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Evaluation of Resources for Teaching of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Courses in Technical Colleges in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated adequacy or otherwise of the human resources available for teaching/learning and training in technical colleges. It examined the state of infrastructural and instructional facilities available, and determined the influence of adequacy or non-adequacy of human and/or infrastructural and instructional resources on the teaching/learning and training in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria. It used descriptive survey. The population for the study comprised all the teachers and the principals in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria. The sample comprised twenty-nine participants. Structured questionnaire (inventory) designed by the researcher was used to collect data. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analysed data. The results showed there is inadequacy of teachers and instructors, and infrastructural and instructional materials are not adequately available in VTCs in Osun State, Nigeria.

Keywords

vocational/technical education, human resources, instructional resources, teaching, training

1 Introduction

In Nigerian National Policy on Education (NPE), technical and vocational education and training (TVET) is put under the Post-Basic Education and Career Development (FRN, 2014: iii). Technical colleges are one of the institutions in which learners acquire knowledge and receive their vocational trainings. The goals of TVET are laudably set and the features of the curricular are significantly enumerated in the NPE.

Technical and vocational colleges (TVCs) in Nigeria are established by the government to inculcate work skills into the prospective learners. For the TVET to meet the aspirations of the stakeholders there is need for provision of adequate resources both in terms of human, infrastructural and instructional. In recent times, there has been a serious concern about the capability of the technical colleges to produce adequately trained and skilled college completers who have requisite work skills in the labour market and/or who are equipped enough for self-employment or self-reliance and have ability to create jobs.

Though several studies (Kagara et al, 2017; Ogunode, 2020) have been carried out in the area of technical and vocational studies, there is dearth of literature on evaluation of resources for teaching of technical and vocational education and training courses in technical colleges in Nigeria in general and Osun State in Particular. According to Vo (2018, 140) citing Stufflebeanm, (2003, 34) evaluation is

“the process of obtaining, providing, and applying descriptive and judgmental information about the merit and worth of some object’s goals, design, implementation, and outcomes to guide improvement decisions, provide accountability reports, inform institutionalization/dissemination decisions, and improvement decisions, and understanding of the involved phenomena”.

To this end, this study becomes very germane.

2 Research objectives and questions

2.1 Objectives

The main objective of the study is to evaluate resources available for teaching/learning and training courses in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Investigate adequacy or otherwise of the human resources available for teaching/learning and training in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria;
- ii. Examine the state of infrastructural and instructional facilities available for teaching/learning and training in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria; and,
- iii. Determine the influence of adequacy or non-adequacy of human and/or infrastructural and instructional resources on the teaching/learning and training in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria.

2.2 Research questions

- i. How adequate are the human resources available for teaching/learning and training in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the state of infrastructural and instructional facilities available for teaching/learning and training in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria?

2.3 Research hypothesis: There is no significant influence of human resources on the learning outcomes of students in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria.

3 Methodology

Research design used was descriptive survey. The population for the study comprised all the teachers and the principals in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria. There are 9 VTCs in the State. Three technical colleges were randomly selected one from each of the three senatorial districts in the State. The actual population size is not known. According to MaCorr Research Solutions Online (2022), the population size is ignored when it is ‘large’ or unknown. The sample respondents consisted of the three principals and all the teachers in the selected VTCs. Thus, the actual total sample was determined after the actual numbers of Principals, and teachers were ascertained. The actual sample, therefore, comprised three principals and twenty-six teachers totalling 29 participants.

The instrument was an open-ended and structured questionnaire (inventory) designed by the researcher and used to assess the on-site infrastructure and instructional facilities in the VTCs. The questionnaire was termed Evaluation of Resources for Teaching Vocational Education and Training Principal’s Questionnaire (ERTVETPQ), and Evaluation of Resources for Teaching Vocational Education and Training Teacher’s Questionnaire (ERTVETTQ). Section A of the questionnaire contained demographic variables of the respondents while Section B contained the list of recommended facilities expected to be available in the VTCs.

3.1 Data analysis

The data were analysed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistics.

4 Results Analysis

Due to the constraint of 2000 words limit for this write-up, tabular analyses of results are put in appendix for necessary perusal.

4.1 Research Question One: How adequate are the human resources available for teaching/learning and training in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 1

Student-Teacher ratio for assessing the adequacy of human resources for teaching/learning and training courses in technical colleges in Osun State

S/n	Departments	No of Teachers	No of Students	Student-Teacher Ratio	Decision	Principal's Remark
Government Technical College, Town Y						
1.	Carpentry and Woodworks	3	92	1:31	Inadequate	Inadequate
2.	Electrical Engineering	5	184	1:37	Inadequate	Adequate
3.	Automobile Mechanical Engineering	4	142	1:36	Inadequate	Adequate
4.	Catering	0	0	0	Not Applicable	Not Applicable
5.	Building: Brick laying and Concrete	3	132	1:44	Inadequate	Inadequate
Government Technical College, Town Z						
1.	Carpentry and Woodworks	2	35	1:18	Adequate	Adequate
2.	Electrical Engineering	3	145	1:49	Very Inadequate	Inadequate
3.	Automobile Mechanical Engineering	1	28	1:28	Inadequate	Very Inadequate
4.	Catering	1	18	1:18	Adequate	Inadequate
5.	Building: Brick laying and Concrete	2	42	1:21	Inadequate	Inadequate
Government Technical College, Town X						
1.	Carpentry and Woodworks	0	0	0	Not Applicable	Not Applicable
2.	Electrical Engineering	2	145	1:49	Very Inadequate	Inadequate
3.	Automobile Mechanical Engineering	0	0	0	Not Applicable	Not Applicable
4.	Catering	0	0	0	Not Applicable	Not Applicable
5.	Building: Brick laying and Concrete	2	42	1:21	Adequate	Very Adequate

Source: Researcher's field work, February, 2023.

Results in Table 1 showed that human resources (teachers) are not adequate in all the three colleges for all the trade options under consideration except carpentry and woodworks and catering in GTC, Ile-Ife and Building: Brick Laying and Concrete at GTC, Gbongan. The summary of the results presented in Table 4.1 is provided in Table 2.

Table 2

Summary of student-teacher ratio for assessing the adequacy of human resources for teaching/learning and training courses in technical colleges in Osun State

	School Locations	Trade Subjects options				
		CWW	EE	AME	CCP	BBC
Adequacy of Human Resources	GTC, Town Y	Inadequate	Inadequate	Inadequate	—	Inadequate
	GTC, Town Z	Adequate	Very Inadequate	Inadequate	Adequate	Inadequate
	GTC, Town X	—	Inadequate	—	—	Adequate

Source: Researcher's field work, February, 2023.

Key: CWW: Carpentry and Wood works; EE: Electrical Electronics; AME: Automobile Mechanical Engineering; CCP: Catering Craft Practice; BBC: Building, Bricklaying and Concrete

4.2 Research Question Two: What is the state of infrastructural and instructional facilities available for teaching/learning and training in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria?

In order to answer this question, the responses of the teachers on the availability or otherwise of recommended infrastructural and instructional facilities were collated. The results obtained are as presented in Tables 3 to 7.

Table 3

State of infrastructural and instructional facilities for teaching and learning Carpentry and Woodwork in Technical Colleges in Osun State

S/N	Items	Not Available	Available but...			
			Not Adequate	Very Adequate	Not Adequate	Adequate
1	Carpentry Workshop	0	0	0	4	1
2	Classrooms	0	0	1	4	0
3	Electricity/Solar Power Supply	1	0	2	2	0
4	Water Supply	0	1	4	0	0
5	Chairs and Tables	0	0	4	1	0
6	Claw Hammer	0	0	4	1	0
7	Tape Measure	0	0	2	1	2
8	Measuring Squares	0	0	2	1	2
9	Chisels	0	0	3	1	0
10	Mallets	0	0	3	1	0
11	Handsaw	0	0	2	3	0
12	Backsaw	0	1	4	0	0
13	Curve Cutting Saw	0	2	3	0	0
14	Planes	0	0	2	3	0
15	Sharpening Stone	0	0	2	3	0
16	Grinder	0	2	3	0	0
17	Hand Drill	0	2	3	0	0

18	Screwdrivers	0	2	2	1	0
19	Clamps	0	0	2	3	0
20	Power Drill	2	0	3	0	0
21	Jigsaw	1	0	3	1	0
22	Circular Saw	0	1	3	1	0
23	Router	2	1	2	0	0
24	Sander	2	1	2	0	0
25	Biscuit Joiner	2	1	2	0	0
26	Table Saw	0	1	4	0	0
27	Radial Arm Saw	3	0	2	0	0
28	Band Saw	2	1	2	0	0
29	Planer	0	1	2	2	0
30	Lathe	1	1	2	0	0
31	Universal Machine	2	1	2	0	0
32	Carpenter's Pencil	1	0	2	1	1
33	Extension Cords	1	0	4	0	0
34	Miter Box	1	0	4	0	0
35	Bench Hook	0	0	2	3	0
36	Woodworking Vise	0	0	5		0
37	Dust Collection System	2	1	1	0	0
38	Workbench	0	0	5	0	0
39	Pegboard	2	1	2	0	0
40	Tool Belt	2	1	2	0	0
41	Scrap Bin	2	1	2	0	0
42	Goggles	0	0	3	2	0
43	Heating Protectors	2	1	2	0	0
44	Respirator	3	0	2	0	0
45	Hair Ties	2	1	2	0	0
46	Push Stick	0	1	2	2	0

Source: Researcher's field work, February, 2023.

Table 3 showed that 43.45% of the facilities are not available at all. The facilities not available are medium-heavy duty machines and disposables/reusable non-capital-intensive materials. A larger percentage of the respondents ranging from 1 (20%) to 5 (100%) highlighted that these facilities are not adequately available. Only one respondent highlighted that each of carpentry workshop and carpenters' pencil are very adequate.

Table 4

State of infrastructural and instructional facilities for teaching and learning Electrical Engineering in Technical Colleges in Osun State.

n=10

S/N	Items	Not Available	Available but....			
			Not Very Adequate	Not Adequate	Adequate	Very Adequate
1	Electrical Laboratory/Workshop	0	3	1	6	0
2	Classrooms	0	3	1	6	0
3	Electricity/Solar Power Supply	7	0	1	2	0
4	Water Supply	2	2	1	4	1
5	Chairs and Tables		5		4	1

6	Pliers	2	3	3	1	1
7	Screwdrivers	2	2	4	1	1
8	Tape Measure	3	2	3	1	1
9	Hammer	3	2	3	1	1
10	Electrical Tape	4	2	3	0	1
11	Fish Tape	4	2	3	0	1
12	Cable Ties	2	6	1	0	1
13	Lever	6	2	0	2	0
14	Wire and Cable Lugs	4	2	2	0	1
15	Flashlight	7	1	1	1	0
16	Utility Knife	5	3	1	0	1
17	Allen Wrench Set	6	1	1	1	1
18	Coax Connector	6	3	0	0	1
19	Wire Crimper	6	2	1	0	1
20	Non-contact Voltage Tester	6	2	0	1	0
21	Voltmeter/Multimeter	2	4	1	3	0
22	Wire Stripper	7	1	0	1	1
23	Reaming Bit	8	1	0	0	1
24	Conduit Bender	2	3	2	2	1
25	Splicing Connector	5	4	0	1	0
26	Circuit Analyzers	8	2	0	0	0
27	Circuit Finders	8	0	0	0	0
28	Soldering iron	2	2	1	3	0
29	Transformer	3	1	1	1	2
30	Battery (Cells)	5	1	0	2	0

Source: Researcher's field work, February, 2023.

Table 4 revealed that except for electrical laboratory workshops, classrooms, water supply, voltmeter/multimeter and soldering iron which teachers responded to that are just adequate; a significant percentage of the responses from the teachers showed that facilities for teaching electrical engineering options are grossly not available. These later facilities include: power supply, lever, flashlight, Allen wrench, wire crimper, non-contact voltage tester, wire stripper, reaming bit, circuit analyzers, circuit finders, utility knife, splicing conductor and battery (cells).

Table 5

State of infrastructural and instructional facilities for teaching and learning Mechanical Engineering (Motor Vehicle Mechanics) in Technical Colleges in Osun State

n=5

S/N	Items	Not Available	Available but....			
			Not Adequate	Very Adequate	Not Adequate	Adequate
1	Electrical Laboratory/Workshop	2	2	1	0	0
2	Classrooms	1	0	4	0	0
3	Electricity/Solar Power Supply	1	0	0	3	0
4	Water Supply	2	1	2	0	0
5	Chairs and Tables	0	1	3	0	0
6	Protective Gloves	2	0	3	0	0
7	Goggles	1	0	3	0	0
8	Apron	1	1	0	3	0

9	Single Point Cutting Tool	2	0	1	2	0
10	Double Point Cutting Tool	4	0	1	0	0
11	Multi Point Cutting Tool	1	0	4	0	0
12	Pliers	1	0	1	2	0
13	Bench Vise	2	1	2	0	0
14	Holding Clamp	3	1	1	0	0
15	Vernier Calipers	3	1	1	0	0
16	Measuring Tapes & Scales	2	0	1	2	0
17	Ball-peen Hammer	2	0	3	0	0
18	Blacksmith Sledge Hammer	1	1	3	0	0
19	Body Mechanic's Hammer	2	0	3	0	0
20	Brick Hammer	3	0	2	0	0
21	Ratchet & Rocket Set	4	0	1	0	0
22	Screwdrivers Set	2	0	2	0	1
23	Adjustable Wrench Set	0	1	3	0	1
24	Fasteners	3	1	0	1	0
25	Spanners	0	1	3	0	0
26	Drill	2	1	2	0	0
27	Hand Cutter	3	2	0	0	0
28	Dremel	3	2	0	0	0
29	Files	1	1	2	0	1
30	Electrical Fault Detector	4	1	0	0	0

Source: Researcher's field work, February, 2023.

Table 5 indicated that only four of the 30 items are very adequate in provision. The items that are almost not available in all the colleges are: double point cutting tool, ratchet and rocket set, electrical fault detector, holding clamp, vernier calipers, brick hammers, fasteners, hand cutter and dremel which between three and four of the five teachers stated that they are not available.

Table 6

State of infrastructural and instructional facilities for teaching and learning Building: Block Laying and Concrete in Technical Colleges in Osun State

n=5

S/N	Items	Not Available	Available but....			
			Not Adequate	Very Adequate	Not Adequate	Adequate
1	Workshop	0	1	3	1	0
2	Classrooms	0	0	4	1	0
3	Electricity/Solar Power Supply	2	0	3	0	0
4	Water Supply	1	1	2	1	0
5	Chairs and Tables	0	2	2	1	0
6	Sand supplies	3	1	0	1	0
7	Hand Trowel	2	0	1	2	0
8	Iron Square	2	0	1	2	0
9	Spirit Level	2	0	1	2	0
10	Tape Measure	2	0	0	3	0

11	Lines & Pegs	2	0	0	1	0
12	Range	2	0	1	1	1
13	Head pans	2	0	0	2	1
14	Shovel	2	0	0	2	1
15	Digger	2	0	0	2	0
16	Mould (Sizes 7 & 9)	2	0	1	2	0
17	Wheel Barrow	0	3	1	1	0
18	Sheave	2	0	1	1	1
19	Scaffold	2	3	0	0	0
20	Mixer	0	5	0	0	0
21	Excavator	4	1	0	0	0
22	Compactor	2	1	2	0	0

Source: Researcher's field work, February, 2023.

Table 6 showed that at least one of the respondents (20%) responded that the following four items viz.: range, head pans, shovel and sheaves are very adequately available. Otherwise, about 77.27% of the materials and facilities needed for teaching and learning Building: Block Laying and Concrete are deemed not available in the technical colleges.

Table 7

State of infrastructural and instructional facilities for teaching and learning Catering in Technical Colleges in Osun State

S/N	Items	Not Available	Available but....			
			Not Very Adequate	Not Adequate	Adequate	Very Adequate
1	Workshop/Kitchen	0	0	1	0	0
2	Classrooms	0	0	1	0	0
3	Electricity/Solar Power Supply	0	0	1	0	0
4	Water Supply	0	0	0	1	0
5	Chairs and Tables	0	0	1	0	0
6	Refrigerator	0	0	1	0	0
7	Gas Cooker	0	0	1	0	0
8	Electric Oven	0	0	1	0	0
9	Blenders	0	0	1	0	0
10	Mixer	0	0	1	0	0
11	Knives Set	0	0	1	0	0
12	Mixing Bowls	0	0	1	0	0
13	Chopping Board	0	0	1	0	0
14	Rolling pins	0	0	1	0	0
15	Electric Fryers	0	0	1	0	0
16	Frying Pans	0	0	1	0	0
17	Cooking Utensils	0	0	1	0	0
18	Mortars & Pestles	0	0	1	0	0
19	Buckets	0	0	0	1	0
20	Dishes & Plates	0	0	0	1	0
21	Cutleries	0	0	0	1	0

Source: Researcher's field work, February, 2023.

Results in Table 7 showed that all the recommended infrastructural and instructional facilities for teaching and learning Catering are available in the college. However, only four (18.18%) of the listed items are adequately available.

4.3 Research Hypothesis: There is no significant influence of human resources on the learning outcomes of students in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria.

In order to determine if there is no significant influence of human resources on the learning outcomes of students in the technical colleges in Osun State, the performances of the students in Catering Craft Practice (CCP) at GTC Ile-Ife for 2017 National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) were first collated. These performances were however not contrasted with other performances as the other colleges do not offer CCP. The data obtained is as presented in Table 8.

Table 8

Performance of students in Catering Craft Practice at GTC, Town Z

	A	C	P	F
CCP only	0	9	1	1
CCP with other trade subjects taken by students	5	22	4	2

Results in Table 8 did not present any exceptional performance that could be attributed to the low student-teacher ratio. Further data on the performances of the students in Building: Brick Laying and Concreting and other trade subjects were collated at two colleges that offered it were contrasted for influence of adequacy of HR. Results obtained are as presented in Table 9.

Table 9

Chi-square statistics of performance of students in Building: Brick Laying and Concreting and other trade subjects

	A	C	P	F	df	χ^2_{cal}	χ^2_{tab}	P	Decision
GTC Town Y (Inadequate HR)	6	34	25	11	3	3.79	7.82	>0.05	Not Sig
GTC Town Z (Adequate HR)	5	22	11	2					

Analysis of students' performance in order to determine whether to accept or reject the null hypothesis that stated that there is no significant influence of human resource on the learning outcomes of students in technical colleges in Osun State, Nigeria revealed that there is no significant difference between the performance of students in the technical college with adequate HR and their counterparts in the college without adequate HR. The null hypothesis was therefore retained at 0.05 level of significance.

5 Discussion of findings

The findings showed that teachers in the technical colleges are grossly inadequate. This is contrary the recommendation in the Nigerian National Policy on Education in Section 3(b) 51(c), which states that "For effective participation of students in practical works the teacher/students' ratio shall be kept at 1:20 (FRN 2014: 20). Adequate availability of teachers in VTCs is crucial for quality training of students. Akinfolarin, et al (2012), and Moughalu (2018) emphasized that shortage of qualified teachers will result in poor training of students. Adequate availability of qualified personnel is a prerequisite for the successful implementation of VTE programmes.

The findings also revealed that many essential instructional facilities are not available. Where available, they are inadequate. Availability of instructional materials is central to effective teaching, learning and training in VTCs. A qualified and competent teacher will be frustrated in their efforts if there are no relevant infrastructural and instructional facilities to work with. Thus, for effective teaching and learning in VTCs, adequate personnel, materials, and infrastructure must be in place.

Contrary to the expectation that the inadequacies of teachers and instructional materials reported would have significant negative effect on the academic performance of students, the null hypothesis was retained at 0.05 level of significance. However, this does not mean that all is well with the students and their performances. The limitation to obtain enough students examinations' results in GTCs in Ile-Ife and Gbongan might be responsible for this.

6 Conclusions

There is inadequacy of teachers and instructors in VTCs in Osun State, Nigeria. Infrastructural and instructional materials are not adequately available in VTCs investigated. There is high supposition that the academic performance of the students would be negatively impacted due to low personnel and material resources.

7 Recommendations

Osun State Government should employ more qualified teachers into the VTCs in the State.

The State Government in collaboration with parents and non-governmental organizations should provide necessary infrastructure and instructional facilities for proper training of prospective VTCs students in Osun State, Nigeria.

The management and staff of VTCs in the State should do all in their powers to minimize the negative impact of shortage of human and material resources on the academic performance of the VTCs students.

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